

Upper plate faults may contribute to the paleoseismic subsidence record along the central Hikurangi subduction zone, Aotearoa New Zealand

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Introduction

Text S1 includes additional methods for elastic dislocation models, remapping the Pleistocene strandline, and recalculating longer-term uplift rates at Cape Kidnappers. It also includes additional information about constraining slip rates on offshore faults.

Tables S1 and S2 include point data and values for recalculating the uplift rate at Cape Kidnappers using updated elevation and age data.

Fig. S1: map of Pleistocene strandlines and elevation points used in Text S1.

Fig. S2: effects of partial slip on the subduction interface for the listric fault elastic dislocation inversion models.

Fig. S3: influence of the up-dip slip termination on surface deformation (forward model)

Fig. S4-S5: effect of lateral slip extent on surface deformation (comparison of forward and inversion models)

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Text S1.

MIS 5e strandline mapping and uplift constraints

There are several uplifted Pleistocene marine terrace strandlines preserved on Cape Kidnappers (Fig. S1). The central, best-preserved terrace is used in the main text to estimate longer-term uplift. Hull (1985) and Paquet et al. (2011) continued mapping the strandline east and west down to c. 130 m above modern sea level (Fig. S1). They calculate an uplift rate decrease from 1.6 mm/yr to 1.0 mm/yr over c. 4 km distance based on this lower strandline. Interpreting continuity of the strandline, however, is complicated by discontinuous or absent risers and terrace treads and a lack of age control on all strandlines. It is possible that these other strandlines to the east are younger than the central strandline, and any uplift gradient is more gradual. We therefore only use the central, well-preserved strandline for constraints in this study.

Since publication of those studies, additional data involved in the Cape Kidnappers uplift rate calculations has become available or improved and therefore the uplift rate warrants an update. These data include high-resolution lidar, updated age control for marine isotope stages (MIS), and more accurate and more local paleo sea level elevations (rather than global elevations). These features have still not been dated with an absolute method, such as optically stimulated luminescence dating, but are assumed to be MIS5e (e.g., Hull, 1985; Paquet et al., 2011).

We used 2020 lidar-based DEM data (Hawke's Bay Regional Council & Toitū Te Whenua Land Information New Zealand (LINZ), 2020) to extract more accurate elevations along the central Pleistocene strandline (e.g., Hull, 1985; Paquet et al., 2011) to constrain the maximum uplift rate at Cape Kidnappers and compare to elastic dislocation model results (Fig. S1). The strandline is marked by a topographic break between an expansive, gently sloping planar surface and a steep ~50-m-high-riser (Hull, 1985). We subsampled the strandline line segments at the base of the risers into elevation points spaced 20 m apart. We then calculated the average elevation of the elevation points, including a local mean sea level adjustment (-0.147 m) with respect to the NZVD2016 vertical datum. The strandline points are 195.7–211.7 m with a mean elevation of 204.1 m above mean sea level (Table S1–S2).

Hull (1985) estimated a maximum uplift rate of 1.6 mm/yr at Cape Kidnappers based on the global estimated MIS5e age at the time (125 ka), spot heights (c. 210 m), and estimated cover thickness (6 m). Using updated elevations from lidar-based mapping (average 204.1 m above mean sea level), more refined minimum MIS5e age (116 ka) (Muhs, 2002), 6 m non-marine sediment cover (Hull, 1985), and more local MIS5e sea level estimations (+ 2.1 m, from southern Australia) (Murray-Wallace et al., 2016), we calculate a maximum uplift rate of 1.7 mm/yr for central Cape Kidnappers (Table S2).

Upper plate fault forward modeling

We run a suite of forward models to test the sensitivity of Ahuriri Lagoon subsidence to different slip patches. All models use the preferred listric (curved) described in the main text. Ultimately, we have very few constraints on what a real earthquake slip distribution looks like on these faults and thus cannot evaluate which taper or slip extent might be more or less accurate. These models provide an indication of the range of slip that might produce 0.5 m of subsidence at Ahuriri Lagoon despite these uncertainties.

Up-dip slip extent

Figure S3 shows the effect of the up-dip slip extent on surface deformation using forward models. In each figure part (a–d), the slip extent stops at 3 km, 6 km, 9 km, and 12 km from the surface trace of the fault, respectively. These variations change the overall slip area, and thus slightly change the earthquake magnitude. They also affect the uplift peak “sharpness”, i.e., how quickly the surface uplift values change near the fault tip. Ruptures with deeper slip

terminations have smoother uplift profiles than ruptures with shallower slip terminations. Variations in the up-dip slip extent have negligible effect on subsidence at Ahuriri lagoon on these fault models.

Slip taper and down-dip extent

Figs. S6–S8 uses forward models to demonstrate the effect of down-dip slip extent and slip taper width. Within each figure, the taper width is the same (9 km, 15 km, and 21 km, respectively). Peak slip is set to 8 m and slip decreases linearly within the taper width. For parts (a–d) in each figure, the lower slip patch terminus is shifted along dip on the modeled fault surface. For example, in all parts (a), the slip patch includes slip up to 9 km down-dip of the intersection between the upper plate fault and the subduction interface. In parts (d), the slip patch ends 9 km up-dip from the intersection of the upper plate fault and subduction interface (Figs. S6–S8). Comparing equivalent parts (e.g., part (a)) between Figs. S6–S8 shows the effect of different slip taper widths for the same down-dip slip extent. We use a rake of 135 (oblique dextral-reverse slip) for all models since the surface deformation pattern is slightly more complicated than pure reverse and we consider 135 a more realistic rake (see main text). The same patterns apply to other rakes, however.

These sensitivity tests show that shifting the down-dip slip extent also shifts the surface deformation toward or away from the fault trace, as expected. The taper width less directly affects the surface deformation by changing the location of peak slip. For example, Fig. S8d uses a 21 km taper that is offset 9 km up-dip from the lower edge of the upper plate fault. This forward model has the largest distance between peak slip and Ahuriri Lagoon, and thus has the lowest coseismic subsidence at the lagoon (0.29 m). Conversely, in Fig. S5d, the narrow slip taper generates moderate subsidence (0.47 m) at Ahuriri Lagoon with the same termination distance from the lower fault edge.

The variation between all model parts (i.e., combined effects of taper width and slip depth) is c. 0.2 m. This suggests that while slip distribution does ultimately affect the surface deformation, there are many possible slip distributions that can produce subsidence at Ahuriri Lagoon. Earthquakes with shallow peak slip are less likely to produce subsidence large enough to be preserved in the Ahuriri Lagoon sedimentary record.

Effects of inversion-controlled slip distribution and lateral slip terminations

Figs. S3 and S4 show the impact of the inversion slip distribution on surface deformation compared to a forward model. The inversion solves for the slip distribution that maximizes subsidence at Ahuriri Lagoon, given model parameters described in the main text. For oblique rake models (rake 135), the location of maximum surface subsidence is west of the slip patch and for pure reverse models (rake 90), the maximum surface subsidence is directly down-dip to the northwest (i.e., maximum subsidence is opposite to rake direction).

For the reverse rake models, the inversion and forward models have very similar slip distributions and subsidence at Ahuriri Lagoon (Fig. S4). For models with oblique rake, the inversion truncates slip to the east of Ahuriri Lagoon to maximize subsidence there (0.7 m subsidence) (Fig. S5). The forward model, which includes slip along the entire fault, has lower subsidence at Ahuriri Lagoon and peak subsidence farther to the southwest. Subsidence in the forward model is still >0.5 m.

We have very poor constraints on rake for earthquakes on these faults (see main text). These results suggest that if earthquake have an oblique rake, the subsidence observed at Ahuriri lagoon may be sensitive to lateral variations in slip near the lower fault edge. However, the forward models demonstrate that earthquakes of similar can still produce large enough subsidence to be recorded at Ahuriri Lagoon even if slip is not “optimally” located.

Slip rates in Hawke Bay

Fault slip rates in Hawke Bay are derived from near-surface offsets and estimated horizon ages observed in seismic survey profiles (Barnes et al., 2002; Barnes & Nicol, 2004; Paquet et al., 2011). These rates are likely minima because they do not include a strike-slip component and changes in fault dip, and may not reflect the full slip at depth (e.g., Barnes, 2002). Strands of the Kidnappers Ridge and Waimārama faults have published vertical separation rates ranging between 0.3 and 2.0 mm/yr (Fig. 3) (e.g., Mountjoy & Barnes, 2011); for pure reverse slip on a steep fault, this vertical separation rate is nearly equivalent to the full slip rate. If the faults have equal reverse and dextral slip, this equates to full slip rates between 0.5 and 3.0 mm/yr at the fault tip. Slip rates along deeper portions of the fault may be even greater.

Of the simplified faults in the Community Fault Model (CFM), the Waimārama and Kidnapper Ridge faults are the only source options for uplift at Cape Kidnappers (Seebeck et al., 2022). The CFM slip rates on these faults (1.0–1.5 mm/yr) are likely underestimates for several reasons. First, the longer-term uplift in central Cape Kidnappers is 1.7 mm/yr; this rate can be used as a minimum constraint for a vertical separation rate on the faults. Even on a fairly steep fault (70 degree dip) with a pure reverse rake, this equates to 2.0 mm/yr full slip rate. Other factors may contribute to a higher full slip rate, such as oblique slip and changes in dip with depth (see above). Additionally, the terrace-derived uplift rate omits subsidence due to flexural-isostatic support of thickened crust; thus, permanent uplift may underestimate cumulative uplift from repeated earthquakes.

Slip rates on nearby structures also highlight a potential underestimate of on the Kidnappers Ridge and Waimārama faults in the CFM. The CFM slip rates are 2.5–4.5 mm/yr on the Lachlan fault and up to 3.0 mm/yr on the southern Kairakau fault (Fig. 1 in main text) (Seebeck et al., 2022). Based on the estimated slip rates above, average slip rates may be more uniform across all Hawke Bay fault zones, rather than decreasing across the Waimārama and Kidnappers Ridge faults.

For the purposes of the main paper, we adopt a minimum slip rate of 2.0 mm/yr on our simplified upper plate fault that spans the Kidnappers Ridge and Waimārama faults. We suggest, however, that actual full slip rates are likely much higher and warrant further investigation.

Figure S1. Uplifted marine terraces and strandlines near Cape Kidnappers. The marine isostope stage (MIS) 5e strandline is used to estimate long-term uplift rates since c. 120 ka. (a) Location of strandlines and other sites. The uplifted Holocene terraces (red circles) represent at least one earthquake since c. 2300 yr BP (Hull, 1987). Active faults from Langridge et al., (2016). (b) Closer view of the MIS5e strandline (break in topography from flatter to steep) and elevation points used for calculations (see Table S1). Elevation raster is overlain on a slope-shaded raster. Lidar DEM data from Hawke's Bay Regional Council & Toitū Te Whenua Land Information New Zealand (LINZ), 2020. AMSL = above modern sea level. Coordinate system = NZTM 2000.

(a) Listic upper plate fault + subduction interface, rake = 90

(b) Listic upper plate fault + subduction interface, rake = 135

Figure S2. Elastic dislocation model results for listric and planar upper plate faults, allowing for some slip on the subduction interface. These models invert for maximum slip at Ahuriri Lagoon. (a) On a reverse rake fault model, additional fault area on the subduction interface does not increase the subsidence at Ahuriri lagoon compared to just the upper plate fault (see Fig. 4 in main text). (b) On the oblique slip fault model, additional fault area on the subduction zone interface allows subsidence up to 0.96 m, which is greater than the upper-plate-only fault model (Fig. 4 in main text).

Figure S3: Influence of updip rupture extent on displacement at Ahuriri Lagoon. (a-d) show the same downdip rupture extent, maximum slip, and taper width but vary by their updip slip limit on the fault surface. The updip extent has little-to-no effect on subsidence at Ahuriri Lagoon, except to reduce the overall slip area and thus minorly changes (0.01 m) the magnitude of subsidence there. Upper plate fault geometry is the same as the listric fault used in the main text; rake is 90.

(a) Listic upper plate fault, inversion

(b) Listic upper plate fault, forward model 12 km taper

Figure S4. Comparing the effects of slip distribution on subsidence at Ahuriri Lagoon (A.L.). Both models shown in (a) and (b) use the same listric fault geometry, peak slip (8 m), and rake (90). Model (a) uses an inversion that solves for the slip distribution that produces maximum subsidence at A.L. (same as shown in main text Fig. 4). Model (b) is a forward model with a 12 km taper on the lateral and lower fault edges. Surface subsidence reaches a maximum above the southwestern lower fault edge for oblique rake; thus, slip distributions that terminate near or northwest Ahuriri Lagoon (at depth) are more likely to produce subsidence >0.5 m.

(a) Listric upper plate fault; inversion

(b) Listric upper plate fault; forward model 12 km taper

Figure S5. Comparing the effects of slip distribution with oblique rake on subsidence at Ahuriri Lagoon (A.L.). Both models shown in (a) and (b) use the same listric fault geometry, peak slip (8 m), and rake (135). Model (a) uses an inversion that solves for the slip distribution that produces maximum subsidence at A.L. (same as shown in main text Fig. 4). Model (b) is a forward model with a 12 km taper on the lateral and lower fault edges. Surface subsidence reaches a maximum above the southwestern lower fault edge for oblique rake; thus, slip distributions that terminate near or northwest Ahuriri Lagoon (at depth) are more likely to produce subsidence >0.5 m.

Figure S6. Influence of down-dip rupture extent and taper on displacement at Ahuriri Lagoon (A.L.). (a-d) show the same down-dip rupture extent, maximum slip, and taper width but vary by their up-dip slip limit on the fault surface. The up-dip extent has little-to-no effect on subsidence at Ahuriri Lagoon, except to reduce the overall slip area and thus minorly changes (0.01 m) the magnitude of subsidence there. Upper plate fault geometry is the same as the listric fault used in the main text; rake is 90 (reverse).

Figure S7. Influence of down-dip rupture extent on displacement at Ahuriri Lagoon (A.L.) with a 15 km lower slip taper. (a-d) show the same up-dip rupture extent, rake, maximum slip, and slip taper but vary in the termination location at depth. Distances in headers are measured along dip from the intersection of the upper plate fault (UPF) and subduction interface (intersection shown by black dashed line). Subsidence at A.L. is maximized when slip terminates at depth below A.L.

Figure S8. Influence of down-dip rupture extent on displacement at Ahuriri Lagoon (A.L.) with a 21 km lower slip taper. (a-d) show the same up-dip rupture extent, rake, maximum slip, and slip taper but vary in the termination location at depth. Distances in headers are measured along dip from the intersection of the upper plate fault (UPF) and subduction interface (intersection shown by black dashed line). Subsidence at A.L. is maximized when slip terminates at depth below A.L.

SSE extent + SEE gap

Figure S9. Forward elastic dislocation model results of a hypothetical subduction interface earthquake. Slip occurs within the upper slow-slip event patch and in the gap between slow slip events. The large magnitude and down-sip slip termination below Ahuriri Lagoon produces substantial (>1 m) coseismic subsidence there.

NZTM Easting (m)	NZTM Northing (m)	lidar DEM elevations (m)	elevation adjusted for NZVD ₂₀₁₆ vertical datum (-0.147 m)
1946686.01	5601840.54	195.92	195.77
1946705.98	5601839.60	197.59	197.44
1946117.02	5601630.00	199.62	199.47
1946136.96	5601629.19	199.63	199.49
1946097.03	5601629.95	200.03	199.89
1946078.46	5601622.53	200.59	200.44
1945749.88	5601534.56	201.59	201.45
1945445.51	5601534.45	201.74	201.60
1946222.35	5601643.71	202.89	202.74
1946205.71	5601632.79	203.09	202.94
1945730.35	5601530.28	203.24	203.09
1945883.70	5601577.51	203.93	203.78
1945432.29	5601549.29	204.06	203.91
1945713.32	5601520.61	204.78	204.63
1945863.70	5601577.51	204.92	204.77
1945379.47	5601569.39	205.13	204.98
1945698.28	5601507.46	205.19	205.05
1945399.44	5601570.47	205.91	205.76
1945417.77	5601562.72	206.00	205.85
1945845.07	5601572.16	206.39	206.24
1945829.00	5601560.64	206.46	206.31
1946459.59	5601698.59	206.53	206.38
1946450.32	5601681.19	206.97	206.83
1945221.60	5601353.52	209.61	209.46
1945263.59	5601395.69	210.03	209.89
1945250.13	5601380.89	211.83	211.68
1945234.11	5601369.05	211.88	211.73

Table S1. Point coordinates along the MIS_{5e} paleostrandline on Cape Kidnappers (See Fig. S1) used in uplift rate recalculations.

adjusted elevation min. (m)	adjusted elevation max. (m)	mean point elevation (adjusted) (m)	MIS _{5e} sea level elevation (m)	non-marine sediment cover (m)	uplift (m)	MIS _{5e} minimum age (ka)	updated uplift rate (mm/yr)
195.77	211.73	204.45	2.1	6	196.35	116	1.7

Table S2. Strandline elevation points and other values used in uplift rate calculations (See text S1).

References

- Barnes, P. M., & Nicol, A. (2004). Formation of an active thrust triangle zone associated with structural inversion in a subduction setting, eastern New Zealand. *Tectonics*, 23(1), n/a-n/a. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2002TC001449>
- Barnes, P. M., Nicol, A., & Harrison, T. (2002). Late Cenozoic evolution and earthquake potential of an active listric thrust complex above the Hikurangi subduction zone, New Zealand. *GSA Bulletin*, 114(11), 1379–1405. [https://doi.org/10.1130/0016-7606\(2002\)114<1379:LCEAEP>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1130/0016-7606(2002)114<1379:LCEAEP>2.0.CO;2)
- Hull, A. G. (1985). *Late Quaternary geology of the Cape Kidnappers area: Hawke's Bay, New Zealand* [Master's Thesis]. Victoria University of Wellington.
- Mountjoy, J. J., & Barnes, P. M. (2011). Active upper plate thrust faulting in regions of low plate interface coupling, repeated slow slip events, and coastal uplift: Example from the Hikurangi Margin, New Zealand. *Geochemistry, Geophysics, Geosystems*, 12(1), n/a-n/a. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2010GC003326>
- Muhs, D. R. (2002). Evidence for the timing and duration of the last interglacial period from high-precision Uranium-series ages of corals on tectonically stable coastlines. *Quaternary Research*, 58(1), 36–40. <https://doi.org/10.1006/qres.2002.2339>
- Murray-Wallace, C. V., Belperio, A. P., Dosseto, A., Nicholas, W. A., Mitchell, C., Bourman, R. P., Eggins, S. M., & Grün, R. (2016). Last interglacial (MIS 5e) sea-level determined from a tectonically stable, far-field location, Eyre Peninsula, southern Australia. *Australian Journal of Earth Sciences*, 63(5), 611–630. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08120099.2016.1229693>
- Paquet, F., Proust, J.-N., Barnes, P. M., & Pettinga, J. R. (2011). Controls on active forearc basin stratigraphy and sediment fluxes: The Pleistocene of Hawke Bay, New Zealand. *Geological Society of America Bulletin*, 123(5–6), 1074–1096. <https://doi.org/10.1130/B30243.1>
- Seebeck, H., Van Dissen, R. J., Litchfield, N. J., Barnes, P. M., Nicol, A., Langridge, R. M., Barrell, D. J. A., Villamor, P., Ellis, S. M., & Rattenbury, M. S. (2022). *New Zealand Community Fault Model—Version 1.0*. <https://doi.org/10.21420/GA7S-BS61>